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“STARTING A BUSINESS”

Starting a business is not an easy task. Due to its intricate process of planning, observing and creating, business usually comes at a cost, may it be physically, mentally, or financially. This cost is necessary to achieve the ideal goal of successfully starting your business, and some may call it a ‘risk’ that you have to be willing to take. Moreover, business requires a good combination of perseverance and determination to do it.

Preparing to start a business usually involves investing your time investigating and observing the place and the product you want to sell. The basic principles of selling a product start with its demand within the area, determining the feasibility of whether such a product is going to sell in that area and the possibility of garnering an income that is more than the cost of your production. In doing so, it is also important to consider the price of your product. Can the people in the area afford the price of your product? If so, do seasonal changes affect the number of customers in that area?

These questions are necessary in order to determine the success of a business. However, you must take note of other competitors in the area of your business. The existence of other competitors is a sign of a good market, but also poses a good challenge to you. When you have competitors in the area, it is advisable to observe and, in return, make appropriate adjustments to your plans and make your product stand out amongst them, such as introducing a special sale or coupons to entice customers to buy from you. Still, making your product stand out will require careful consideration since it is another risk that you’ll be taking. Simply giving out discounts and sales may attract many customers. However, it may also affect the profits of your business at the same time.

Despite the risk and the need to sacrifice time, comfort and money, starting up a business from scratch is a great achievement in the long run. This means that all your effort, sacrifices and skills will pay off when your business is built with thorough planning, investigation, market research, commitment and perseverance.